

1 **Table S2** Media composition for the peripheral inflammation model

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DIV	SOMAL COMPARTMENT 200 μ L/well		AXONAL COMPARTMENT 100 μ L/well	
DIV 0	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
DIV 1	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	50 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	50 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL
5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL	
DIV 3	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL
DIV 5	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 μ g/mL
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 μ g/mL
			Bradykinin (Sigma)	1 μ M
			PGE-2 (Sigma)	10 μ M
			Histamine (Sigma)	10 μ M
			5-HT (Sigma)	10 μ M
			ATP (Sigma)	15 μ M

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5 **Table S3** Media composition for the chemotherapy induced peripheral neuropathy model

DIV	SOMAL COMPARTMENT 200 µL/well		AXONAL COMPARTMENT 100 µL/well	
DIV 0	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	2%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
DIV 2 DIV 7	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	5%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	5%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL
	FBS	5%	FBS	5%
NaCl	5 mg/mL	NaCl	5 mg/mL	
DIV 5	Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)		Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%	GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	5%	B27 Supplement (Gibco)	5%
	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%	Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	25 ng/mL	mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
	hGDNF (PeproTech)	25 ng/mL	hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL	Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL
	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL	5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL
	FBS	5%	FBS	5%
NaCl	5 mg/mL	NaCl	5 mg/mL	
		Paclitaxel (Tocris) or DMSO (Sigma)	1 µM or 0,04%	
DIV 6			Neurobasal growth medium(Gibco)	
			GlutaMAX (Gibco)	1%
			B27 Supplement (Gibco)	5%
			Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco)	1%
			mNGF 25 s (Promega)	100 ng/mL
			hGDNF (PeproTech)	100 ng/mL
			Uridine (Sigma)	17,5 µg/mL
			5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (Sigma)	7,5 µg/mL
			FBS	5%
		NaCl	5 mg/mL	

1 **Table S4** Quantification of percentage of response (mean +/- SD) of DRGs from females and
 2 males mice to capsaicin, menthol or AITC. Statistical analysis two-way ANOVA. N=4
 3 animals.

	CAPS	MENT	AITC	KCI	P value 0.8348
DRGs female	12.3 ± 7.8	9.15 ± 6.3	8.0 ± 8.3	56.2 ± 29.7	
DRGs male	11.9 ± 6.4	10.5 ± 7.9	7.8 ± 1.7	51.0 ± 26.2	

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 5 **Table S5** Quantification of the size of the responses (mean +/- SD) of DRGs from females
 6 and males mice to capsaicin, menthol or AITC. Statistical analysis two-tailed Mann-Whitney
 7 U. N=4 animals.

	CAPS	MENT	AITC	KCI
DRGs female	0.56 ± 0.51	0.47 ± 0.44	0.48 ± 0.41	0.79 ± 0.46
DRGs male	0.51 ± 0.48	0.51 ± 0.28	0.54 ± 0.37	0.76 ± 0.48
P value	0.6958	0.0552	0.2578	0.4815

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 9 **Table S6.** Quantification of percentage of response (mean +/- SD) of DRGs or DRG-
 10 keratinocytes to capsaicin, menthol, AITC or KCI. Statistical analysis two-way ANOVA.

	CAPS	MENT	AITC	KCI	P value < 0.0001
DRGs	12.1 ± 6.9	9.8 ± 6.8	7.9 ± 6.9	53 ± 28.1	
DRGs-KER	27.4 ± 11.7	31.5 ± 8.3	24.4 ± 10.7	70.2 ± 24.9	

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1 **Table S7.** Quantification of percentage of response (mean +/- SD) to capsaicin, menthol,
 2 AITC or KCl of DRGs or DRGs co-cultured with keratinocytes medium+NGF+GDNF in the
 3 axonal compartment. Statistical analysis two-way ANOVA.

	CAPS	MENT	AITC	KCI	P value 0.8635
DRGs medium	12.1 ± 6.9	9.8 ± 6.8	7.9 ± 6.9	53 ± 28.1	
HaCaT medium (no ker)	12.7 ± 10.8	7.1 ± 5.1	8.3 ± 8.7	53.9 ± 31.9	

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Table S8. RT-qPCR primers for mouse TRPA1, TRPM8, CGRP (CALCA), Substance P (SP, Tac1) and P2X3.

Target	Primer FW	Primer RV
TRPA1	GCAGGTGGAACCTTCATACCAACT	CACTTTGCGTAAGTACCAGAGTGG
TRPM8	CTTTCTAAGCAATGGTATGGAG	GGTTTCTTCCTAAATGATACGAG
CGRP	TTTCCTGGTTGTCAGCATCTT	GCGAACTTCTTCTTCACTGAGAGT
SP	TTTTCTCGTTTCCACTCAACTGT	TCTGCAGAAGATGCTCAAGG
P2X3	AAAGCTGGACCATTGGGATCA	CGTGTCCCGCACTTGGTAG

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